

Effects of Whole Blood Storage on Hematological Parameters of Sudanese Donors attending Central Blood Bank

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Abstract:

Background: During storage of blood several hematological and biochemical changes take place that may affect viability of blood cells and other components. In Sudan (to our knowledge) there is no enough information about these changes and there are some gaps in the studies that have been conducted, it did not include all hematological parameters, thus the aim of the present study is to study the various hematological changes occurring in stored whole blood.

Methods: This is cross-sectional study conducted at Central Blood Bank, Khartoum state. The study conducted in the period from

October 2019 to February 2020, included 100 Sudanese adults donors at defined age group (18-48). The Complete Blood Count (CBC) was performed on it immediately at the time of collection, and this was considered as control, then CBC performed at 1,2,3,4 weeks using automated cell count (Sysmex KY21N).

Results: In the first and second weeks there were insignificant changes in all hematological parameters except for platelets, there was a significant decrease started from first week (2.086 vs 3.286; p value =.005) compared to the control, while in third and fourth weeks all changes that occurred with a significant decrease, except for the MCV, which was significant increase in fourth week (90.725 vs. 87.846; p value =.001) compared to the control.

Conclusions: All hematological parameters that evaluated above affected by storage, but platelets are more affected which have significant decrease in Day 7.

Keywords: *Transfusion, Whole blood, storage, lesion, haemotherapy.*

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a vast improvement in the organisation, management, clinical and technical aspects of transfusion services in sub-Saharan Africa, although serious concerns remain with regard to the safety and adequacy of the blood supply (Nkohkwo, et al., 2016). According to the WHO recommended minimum of 10 units of donated blood per 1000 catchment population, an estimated 8–9 million units of blood are currently needed per year for transfusion in Africa (World Health Organization, 2009).

Blood is collected into a plastic bag for blood donation. One blood unit consisted of 450 ml of blood mixed with anticoagulant; these include citrate –phosphate dextrose (CPD), acid – citrate dextrose (ACD), with adenine to prolong red cell storage (Lave, Jones, & Williamson, 2000; Hebert, & Chin-Yee, 2000).

Whole blood may be preserved for up to 21 days, without losing its usefulness in blood transfusions an anticoagulant is added to prevent clotting blood plasma, the fluid portion of the blood, may be frozen and / or dried and stored indefinitely (Hebert, & Chin-Yee, 2000).

Despite the use of additive solutions, changes in RBC morphology and metabolism are expected during the storage of blood bags with and without leuko-reduction. Storage of erythrocytes causes some complex structural and biochemical alterations, which are called red cell storage lesion (RCSL) (Ghezelbash, et al., 2018).

Also, there are some biochemical and hematological changes occur (generally known as storage lesion), which can affect the efficacy of blood transfusion (Saran, 2003).

Blood transfusion in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) is at a crossroad. Significant recent developments may help meet local needs in safe blood products and fulfil a global health target, as highlighted by the World Health Organization (WHO) Millennium and Sustainable Development Goals, in improving supply and safety, and ensuring the gradual implementation selective haemotherapy (Barro, et al., 2018). Additionally,

WHO recommends that all activities related to blood collection, testing, processing, storage and distribution be coordinated at the national level through effective organization and integrated blood supply networks (World Health Organization, n.d.). Accordingly; there is a growing interest to evaluate the changes that may occur during storage of blood considering fixed storage conditions.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This is cross-sectional study conducted at Central Blood Bank, Khartoum state. The study conducted in the period from October 2019 to February 2020, included 100 Sudanese adults donors at defined age group (18-48), excluded individuals who are not met the criteria for blood donation.

Data Collection and Sampling Technique

The data was collected using laboratory investigation to obtain complete blood count also a questionnaire was used. (See appendix A) by Non Probability Voluntary sampling technique.

Specimen Collection

Three milliliters venous blood sample was collected by disposable plastic syringe from fresh blood at the time of collection as control (day 0). Then same amount of blood was taken from stored blood (350 mL blood + 49 mL CPDA-1), at different intervals (day7, day14, day21and day28). The blood was slowly poured into 2 tetra acetic acid (EDTA) anticoagulant blood containers. -gentle and adequate mixing of sample was applied by mixture to avoid hemolysis, clot or platelet aggregation.

Automated Cell Count (Sysmex Device)

EDTA blood samples were analyzed for CBC using Sysmex automated hematological analyzer.

Ethical Consideration

It was considered that all information obtained from participants was kept as highly confidential data and specimen's results were not permitted.

The participants were provided with information about the study and any risk which may be raised especially when the collection technique was applied.

Results

This study was conducted at the central blood bank in the state of Khartoum on one hundred

adult donors at defined age group (18-48). All of them are males, beginning in August and ending in February, to study hematological changes that occur during storage of whole blood (450ml from blood+49ml from CPDA-1). All samples collected from donors who met the specifications required to donate blood. The CBC was performed on it immediately after first collection, and this was considered as the control, then CBC performed at 1,2,3,4 weeks. The results of each week were compared with the control. All conditions related to blood storage are kept in all stages of the examination.

Figure1. Show Distribution Age of Participants in the Study

Note: The mean value(\bar{X}) \pm Standard Error Mean (SEM) are performed

In the first week there was insignificant changes in all hematological parameters except for platelets, there was a decrease significantly (mean

of plt in first week =2.086 and p value =.005) compared to the control (mean of plt in control = 3.286) showed in tables 1.

Table 1. Show Statistical Results of CBC and Their P-Values in First Week

	Control	First week	p-value1
RBCs $\times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$	5.1121	5.0963	0.872
Hb g/dl	15.1777	14.539	0.115
PCV%	45.856	44.137	0.794
MCV/ fl	87.846	86.359	0.138
MCH P.g	30.4091	29.130	0.281
MCHC g/dl	32.428	31.513	0.183
PLT $\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$	3.2863	2.0867	0.005
TWBCS $\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$	6.3804	5.9330	0.114

Neutrophil x10 ³ µl	2.7432	2.538	0.108
Lymphocyte x10 ³ µl	2.9929	2.2753	0.162
Monocyte x10 ³ µl	.3519	.3339	0.987
Basophil x10 ³ µl	0.2935	.2575	0.158
Eosinophil x10 ³ µl	0.2875	.1319	0.077

In the second week there was a insignificant changes in all hematological parameters except for platelets, there was a decrease significantly

(mean of plt in second week =1.049 and p value = .001) compared to the control (mean of plt in control = 3.286) showed in table 2.

Table 2. Show Statistical Results of CBC and Their P-Values in Second Week

	Control	Second week	p-value2
RBCs x10 ⁶ µl	5.1121	4.9601	0.071
Hb g/dl	15.1770	14.196	0.096
PCV%	44.8561	43.721	0.089
MCV/ fl	87.8460	87.947	0.074
MCH P.g	28.4091	28.837	0.091
MCHC g/dl	32.4284	31.085	0.092
PLT x10 ³ µl	3.2863	1.049	0.001
TWBCS x10 ³ µl	6.3804	5.0185	0.051
Neutrophil x10 ³ µl	2.7432	2.103	0.095
Lymphocyte x10 ³ µl	2.0729	2.007	0.104
Monocyte x10 ³ µl	.3519	0.2954	0.516
Basophil x10 ³ µl	.2333	0.2108	0.089
Eosinophil x10 ³ µl	.1875	0.2009	0.063

In the third week a significant decrease occurred in all hematological parameters, except for the MCV, in which the change occurred with a

significant increase (mean in third week =89.946, p value=0.026 and mean of control 87.846).

Table 3. Show Statistical Results of CBC and Their P-Values in Third Week

	Control	Third week	p-value3
RBCs x10 ⁶ µl	5.1121	3.752	.044
Hb g/dl	15.1777	13.263	0.042
PCV%	45.856	42.520	0.038
MCV/ fl	87.846	89.964	0.026
MCH P.g	30.4091	27.270	0.045
MCHC g/dl	32.428	29.172	0.033
PLT x10 ³ µl	3.2863	0.902	0.001
TWBCS x10 ³ µl	6.3804	4.856	0.049
Neutrophil x10 ³ µl	2.7432	1.054	0.037
Lymphocyte x10 ³ µl	2.9929	1.543	0.025
Monocyte x10 ³ µl	.3519	0.1722	0.034
Basophil x10 ³ µl	0.2935	0.1843	0.039
Eosinophil x10 ³ µl	0.2875	0.1996	0.028

In the fourth week also, a significant decrease occurred in all hematological parameters, except for the MCV, in which the change occurred with

increase (mean in fourth week =90.725, p value =.001 and mean of control 87.846).

Table 4. Show Statistical Results of CBC and Their P-Values in Fourth Week

	Control	Fourth week	p-value4
RBCs x10 ⁶ _{μl}	5.1121	3.012	0.003
Hb g/dl	15.1777	12.572	0.001
PCV%	45.856	41.610	0.015
MCV/ fl	87.846	90.725	0.001
MCH P.g	30.4091	26.941	0.006
MCHC g/dl	32.428	28.100	0.003
PLT x10 ³ _{μl}	3.2863	0.054	0.00
TWBCS x10 ³ _{μl}	6.3804	3.296	0.009
Neutrophil x10 ³ _{μl}	2.7432	1.001	0.001
Lymphocyte x10 ³ _{μl}	2.9929	1.020	0.000
Monocyte x10 ³ _{μl}	.3519	0.1095	0.00
Basophil x10 ³ _{μl}	0.2935	0.1415	0.000
Eosinophil x10 ³ _{μl}	0.2875	0.1675	0.001

Discussion

This study was conducted to determine the effect of storage varying periods on some hematological parameters. The study includes 100 blood samples admitted to central blood bank in Khartoum State. All samples collected from donors who met the specifications required to donate blood. The CBC was performed on it immediately after first collection (day zero). Day zero was considered as the control, and then CBC performed at 1,2,3,4 weeks. The results of each week were compared with the control.

In the first week and the second week, there was insignificant changes in all hematological parameters except for platelets, there was a decrease significantly (mean of plt in first week =2.086 and p value =.005, while mean in second week =1.049 and p value = .001) compared to the control (mean of plt in control = 3.286) showed in tables 1 and 2.

Our results is similar to the finding of study done on the platelets in the central blood bank in Iraq Mosul, and it found: In fresh whole blood platelets are about 60 % effective at 24 hours and almost completely ineffective after 48 hours (mean of plt in first day =261.3±13.45 and p value = NS, while mean in second day =202.4±9.12 and p value = .01) compared to the control (mean of plt in control = 267.2±13.82). Additionally, the rapid disintegration of platelets during storage may be due to a rapid disappearance of the white blood cells; their hydrolytic enzyme may cause platelet

degeneration via affected platelet membrane. Accordingly, platelets lose viability rapidly on storage in refrigerators; moreover, the platelet viability and functions are affected by white blood cells present in stored platelet concentrate.

Additionally, our finding is agree with study conducted in hematological changes in stored blood in India which is showed: Hemoglobin was significantly affected by storage period of blood (mean of HB in second day =16.50±0.35 and p value = NS, while mean in tenth day =14.72±0.25 and p value = 0.05) compared to the control (mean of HB in control = 16.50 ±0.35), also, PCV was significantly affected by storage period of blood (mean of PCV in second day =44.1±0.79 and p value = NS, while mean in tenth day =42.7±0.86 and p value = 0.01) compared to the control (mean of PCV in control = 44.3 ±0.72). On other hand our results is contrary with a result regarding Total white blood cells in the same Indian study which is showed a significant decreased in the second day (mean of WBCs in first day =5.1±0.25 and p value = NS, while mean in second day =4.2 ±0.21 and p value = 0.01) compared to the control (mean of WBCs in control = 5.2 ±0.28).

The significant decrease in hemoglobin concentration and total red blood cells can be attributed to the hemolysis that occurs during storage (Sawant, et al., 2007).

While white blood cells have an abbreviated life span in stored blood and transfusion proved ineffective in elevating the leukocytes count, the

many studies showed that during storage the total leukocyte count decreases, they attribute this decrease to degeneration of the granulocytes (Van der Meer, & de Wildt-Eggen, 2006).

Interestingly, the current work has compared with findings with study conducted in Nigeria in which the blood bags were screened and noted the result of day 1 versus day 7 which is revealed that the granulocytes were drastically reduced, there was significant changes in WBC, differential and absolute leucocytes, but, no significant changes were observed in Hb, PCV and other hematological parameters throughout the study. This study agree with my results in PCV, Hemoglobin and other hematological parameters but against in Total white blood cells.

Conclusion

All hematological parameters that evaluated above affected by storage, but platelets are more affected which have significant decrease in Day 7.

Recommendation

We recommended that not store blood for more than 7 days if the platelets are target and also, another additive solution must be used to preserve the blood for long time.

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Authors' Contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Ethical Approval and Consent

The study was approved by the research committee at the faculty of medical laboratory

science, Managil University of Science & Technology. Ethical approval was achieved from the university, Informed consents were taken from each subject before enrollment in the study.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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